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Improvement of Methodological Approaches to Assessing Risks in Agribusiness Activities

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ABSTRACT

Agribusiness activities are inherently exposed to a wide range of risks arising from climatic variability, market volatility, technological change, and institutional uncertainty. The effectiveness of managerial decisions in this sector largely depends on the accuracy and adaptability of risk assessment methodologies. This paper aims to improve methodological approaches to assessing risks in agribusiness by integrating traditional risk evaluation tools with modern analytical methods. The study systematizes key types of agribusiness risks and critically reviews existing assessment approaches, identifying their limitations in capturing dynamic and interrelated risk factors. An improved methodological framework is proposed, combining quantitative indicators, qualitative expert assessments, and scenario-based analysis to enhance the reliability of risk evaluation. The proposed approach allows for a more comprehensive identification, measurement, and prioritization of risks, supporting more informed decision-making at both enterprise and policy levels. The findings contribute to the development of more resilient agribusiness management systems and can be applied in strategic planning and risk management practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's market economy, agribusiness entities play a crucial role in ensuring the sustainable economic development of the regions[1]. They provide a significant share of food security, create jobs, and form the socio-economic basis for rural development[2].

Small and medium-sized agribusiness enterprises are characterized by high adaptability to changing external conditions, the ability to flexibly respond to market needs, and quickly implement new business ideas, which allows for the effective use of innovative approaches in agricultural production[3], [4].

For the effective operation of agribusiness entities, it is necessary to systematically identify the main risks arising during the production and sale of agricultural products, to assess their magnitude and probability of occurrence with maximum accuracy, and to justify a set of measures to minimize and manage them[5], [6].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding risk in agribusiness begins with defining what constitutes risk and why its assessment is critical. Risk generally refers to the potential for uncertain events to negatively affect outcomes in production, finance, supply chains, and strategic decision-making. In risk assessment, analytical methodologies aim to characterize both the likelihood of adverse events and the severity of their consequences[7]. Techniques such as probabilistic risk assessment (PRA) systematically estimate these dimensions by combining probability and consequence metrics, rather than purely qualitative judgment. This probabilistic framework originates in engineering risk analysis but has been adapted for economic and environmental applications, including agriculture.

A systematic literature review on agro-food supply chain risk assessment shows that semi-quantitative approaches are the most widely used, followed by quantitative, mixed, and purely qualitative approaches. Semi-quantitative techniques often combine scales, ratings, and categorization with numerical scoring to provide heuristic yet structured assessments[8].

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Across the literature, several methodological themes emerge:

According to M.Muminov a consistent emphasis on structured classification of risks (e.g., climatic vs. economic vs. institutional) underpins methodological design and impacts tool selection. Techniques such as aggregation models, fuzzy logic, and other quantitative tools are increasingly used to assess risk severity and probability in specific agribusiness cases, as seen in supply chain risk assessments[9]. While qualitative, strategic tools such as SWOT analysis are often leveraged to contextualize risk and opportunities within Uzbekistan’s agribusiness environment, providing a basis for hybrid methodological frameworks[10].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs an expert-based research methodology to improve methodological approaches to assessing risks in agribusiness activities. The expert methodology is selected due to the complexity, uncertainty, and multidimensional nature of agribusiness risks, many of which cannot be adequately quantified using purely statistical methods.

The research follows a qualitative–semi-quantitative design, in which expert knowledge is systematically collected, structured, and transformed into measurable indicators. This approach allows the integration of professional experience, sectoral knowledge, and contextual understanding into the risk assessment process.

4. RESULTS

Classification of risks by "area of occurrence" implies their distribution depending on the area in which they are formed and manifested. Generalizing the following main groups (Fig 1).

Risks that are objectively related to the possibility of financial, material, and other losses in the activities of agribusiness arise in the current economic conditions, there is a need for the active formation and effective functioning of a risk management system. This system should ensure optimal risk accounting and management in the process of making and implementing management decisions, which contributes to achieving the strategic and tactical goals of agribusiness activities.

Figure 1. Grouping of risks by "areas of occurrence"

Qualitative analysis of factors influencing the effectiveness of agribusiness activities is aimed at identifying specific risks inherent in a particular type of activity and the stage of its development.

In the course of the study, the essence of risk factors was determined, a description of each of their types was given, as well as the sources of their occurrence and possible consequences of their manifestation. In particular, production factors are characterized by a low level of technical and technological equipment of production, depreciation or breakdown of agricultural machinery and equipment, and other reasons. Among the possible consequences, violation of agrotechnical requirements, deterioration of conditions for keeping and feeding animals, and a decrease in the yield and productivity of agricultural crops can be highlighted. The indicated group of factors belongs to the group of conditionally regulated internal factors. In turn, weather factors arise under the influence of atmospheric and hydrological processes, natural disasters. These factors are external in nature and belong to the category of unregulated factors.

For the quantitative assessment of risk factors influencing the development of agribusiness, various methods of analysis and modeling

are used, aimed at determining the level of probability of risk occurrence and the degree of their impact on the results of economic activity (Table 1).

Table 1. Description of methods for quantitative assessment of risk factors in agribusiness

Methods	Description	Strengths	Weaknesses
Expert evaluation method	It is based on the opinions of specialists with experience and knowledge in the analyzed field.	Takes into account the professional experience of experts; allows assessing factors that are difficult to measure; is used in the absence of statistical data.	Subjectivity; dependence on the qualifications and number of experts; bias.
Statistical method	Analysis of factual data is based on the calculation of probability, variance, correlation, and trends.	High objectivity; reliability in the presence of sufficient data; the possibility of quantitative comparison of factors.	Requires a high-quality and complete database; does not take into account unpredictable or new risks.
Modeling method	Expresses the state of choice in the form of a tree of probability of alternative options and outcomes.	Allows visualization and construction of the problem; takes into account the probability and consequences of solutions; is suitable for complex scenarios.	Difficulty of construction; sensitivity to errors in initial data; requires accurate probability estimation.
Comparison method	Assessment of factors based on comparison with similar situations, objects, or projects.	Simplicity of application; possibility of use with limited data; high efficiency.	Errors due to differences between similar objects; limited applicability in unique conditions.
Combination method	Combines multiple approaches (e.g., expert and statistical) to obtain more accurate results.	Increases the reliability of assessment; allows to compensate for the shortcomings of individual methods; flexibility in application.	Increases the complexity and laboriousness of analysis; requires coordination of various methodological foundations.
Objective method	Based on real data, measurable indicators, and calculations without subjective interference.	High accuracy and reproducibility; independence from the human factor.	Does not take into account qualitative aspects and uncertainty; limited under conditions of data shortage.
Subjective method	The entrepreneur's (business entity's) assumption regarding a specific result.	For a quick solution to the problem, much information is not required.	High degree of subjectivity; probability of disruption; low reproducibility.
Script method	Creating possible scenarios for the development of the situation, taking into account various factors and their probabilities.	Allows to assess alternative development paths; helps in strategic planning; identifies potential threats.	Requires large analytical resources; dependence on the quality of initial assumptions; difficulty in quantitative assessment.

Among the many methods of assessing risks affecting agribusiness activities, it is necessary to choose the most optimal one for solving specific research tasks. The conducted research showed that in the context of the agricultural sector, the expert evaluation method and the statistical method show the highest effectiveness.

The essence of the expert evaluation method consists in conducting an intuitive-logical analysis of the problem under study by specialists, with subsequent quantitative expression of their opinions and formal processing of the obtained data. The final, generalized opinion of the experts, obtained as a result of the systematization and analysis of this data, is accepted as the final solution to the problem under study. A comprehensive combination of intuitive assessments, logical reasoning, and quantitative analysis ensures high effectiveness of decisions made.

Both individual and collective forms of expertise may be used in the implementation of expert assessment. The choice of a particular form depends on the time, financial, and organizational capabilities of the researchers.

Within the framework of this study, the individual method of expert assessment and the method of collective idea generation ("brainstorming") were used in the selection of factors to be included in the questionnaire. The expert questionnaire included 16 factors listed in the appendix. Experts were asked to evaluate each factor on a five-point scale, where 5 points correspond to the highest level of significance.

The algorithm for conducting an expert survey includes the following main stages:

- determination of the purpose of the expert survey;
- formation of a list of factors and development of questionnaires;
- selection and formation of an expert group;
- conducting a survey;
- analysis and processing of the obtained data;
- creation of a map of risk factors.

Points are calculated for each type of risk factor for all experts. Subsequently, the obtained indicators are summarized, and based on them, the BERI index is calculated, reflecting the share of each risk in the total set, taken as 100%. According to which a group of more than 100 experts is considered optimal (Table 2).

Table 2.

Total assessment of risk factors by respondents, %

The position of the risk factor	Name of risk factors	Specific weight of the factor, %
1	Weather	7,83
2	Financial	7,74
3	Sales (commercial)	7,48
4	Qualified	7,14
5	Wages	6,44
6	Change of political course	6,19
7	Regulatory framework	6,15
8	Ecological	6,13
9	Insurance	6,10
10	Demographic	5,90
11	Production	5,84
12	Biological	5,69
13	Investment	5,63
14	Transportation	5,51
15	Migration	5,31
16	Unemployment	4,92
TOTAL:		100

During the study, a combined method was used, representing a synthesis of expert and statistical approaches, to assess the factors influencing the activities of agribusiness. With the help of this method, the integral (generalizing, aggregate) risk indicator R_{total} , characterizing the influence of factors on the activities of all agricultural enterprises, was assessed.

$$R_{жамн} = \sum_{i=1}^n (w_i A_i) , = w_1 A_1 + w_2 A_2 + w_3 A_3$$

If all factors have the same level of importance (i.e., have equal advantages, or there is no system of priorities), then the values of the weighting coefficients are assumed to be equal for all factors.

$$w_1 = \frac{1}{n} = \frac{1}{3} = 0,33$$

If the indicators are arranged in descending order of their significance, they can be calculated according to the Fishburn rule:

$$w_i = \frac{2 * (n - i + 1)}{(n + 1)n}$$

Quantitative assessment of the aggregate risk indicator

$$A_i = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^M A_{ij} g_{ij}$$

At the last stage, the selection of a scale for assessing the level of the risk factor is carried out, on the basis of which the level of integral and basic risks of the studied object is determined. In economic literature, there are many approaches and recommendations for using various scales of permissible risk levels. In this work, the empirical scale of risk levels proposed by V.M. Granaturov was taken as a basis.

Table 3.

Empirical risk scale

№	Risk factor tolerance	Name of risk factor levels
1	0,0-0,1	Minimum
2	0,1-0,3	Small
3	0,3-0,4	Average
4	0,4-0,6	High
5	0,6-0,75	Maximum
6	0,75-1,0	Critical

When compiling a list of factors proposed for the expert group, it is necessary to take into account a number of requirements and characteristics. In particular, the selected factors should be:

- represent the most important and probable conditions and risks for agricultural entrepreneurs;
- causing the most significant losses affecting the economic, financial, organizational, and social performance indicators of agricultural enterprises.

5. CONCLUSION

This study addressed the problem of improving methodological approaches to assessing risks in agribusiness activities under conditions of high uncertainty and limited statistical information. Agribusiness is inherently exposed to a wide range of risks, including production, market, financial, institutional, technological, and environmental risks, which require comprehensive and flexible assessment tools to support effective decision-making.

The research demonstrated that traditional quantitative methods alone are often insufficient to capture the full complexity of agribusiness risks. In this context, the application of an expert-based methodology proved to be a justified and effective approach. By systematically structuring expert knowledge through standardized questionnaires, risk scoring, and consensus techniques, the study transformed qualitative judgments into analytically meaningful indicators.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. A. Gyamerah, P. Ngare, и D. Икре, «Crop yield probability density forecasting via quantile random forest and Epanechnikov Kernel function», 2019, doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.1904.10959.
- [2] Kaluga branch of the Russian State Agrarian University — Moscow Timiryazev Agricultural Academy, Kaluga, Russia, I. N. Turchaeva, V. G. Zabirowa, Kaluga branch of the Russian State Agrarian University — Moscow Timiryazev Agricultural Academy, B. N. Khosiev, и Department of Economics and Economic Security of the Gorsky State Agrarian University, RSO-Alania, Vladikavkaz, «Evaluation of the effectiveness of state support for agribusiness entities», *Accounting in Agriculture*, вып. 8, сс. 485–496, авг. 2023, doi: 10.33920/sel-11-2308-04.
- [3] Kusnandar, N. Setyowati, и E. W. Riptanti, «CREATING AN INNOVATIVE CULTURE IN AGRIBUSINESS OF MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES», *AGRICULTURAL AND RESOURCE ECONOMICS-INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC E-JOURNAL*, т. 9, вып. 2. INST EASTERN EUROPEAN RESEARCH & CONSULTING, EDUC CAMPUS KNAU, KHARKIV, UKRAINE, сс. 205–222, 2023 г. doi: 10.51599/are.2023.09.02.09.
- [4] M. Lutovac Đaković, «THE IMPACT OF VALUED MACROECONOMIC FACTORS BY TOP MANAGEMENT ON BUSINESS IN MEDIUM-SIZED INDUSTRIAL AND MEDIUM-SIZED AGRIBUSINESS ENTERPRISES», *EA*, т. 72, вып. 4, сс. 1223–1242, дек. 2025, doi: 10.59267/ekoPolj25041223L.
- [5] O. O. Pryz, «The role of the institute of trust-based secured ownership in the legal mechanism for the functioning of agribusiness entities», *Науковий вісник УжНУ. Серія: Право*, т. 1, вып. 89, сс. 396–400, июл. 2025, doi: 10.24144/2307-3322.2025.89.1.55.
- [6] Podillia state university и др., «INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE SYSTEM OF FINANCIAL PROVISION OF INTERNATIONAL AGRIBUSINESS ENTITIES», *APE*, т. 1, вып. 284, сс. 54–74, 2025, doi: 10.32752/1993-6788-2025-1-284-54-74.
- [7] Livestock Farming Institute of National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine, D. H. Tsarenko, S. V. Khalin, и Livestock Farming Institute of National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine, «Insurance as a Risk Management Tool in Agribusiness», *PE*, т. 1, вып. 63, сс. 254–260, 2025, doi: 10.32983/2222-0712-2025-1-254-260.
- [8] D. B. Paillin, M. Machfud, H. Hardjomidjojo, и M. Romli, «Agro-Food Supply Chain Risk Assessment: A Review Based on Technique and Approach», *JAETS*, т. 5, вып. 2, сс. 892–908, июн. 2024, doi: 10.37385/jaets.v5i2.3688.
- [9] K. A. Pardaev, «Risk Mitigation Strategies in the Tomato Supply Chain», *Am. J. Agric. Sci. Eng. Technol.*, т. 6, вып. 3, сс. 118–123, ноя. 2022, doi: 10.54536/ajaset.v6i3.863.
- [10] .